

Thermodynamics of 1,10-Phenanthroline Ion and its Iron(II) Complexes in Methanol-Water Mixtures at 298°K

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The equilibrium constants of the "isoelectric" reactions of the type

have been determined *pH*-metrically and spectrophotometrically in methanol-water mixtures in 8-37 wt % in methanol. The enthalpies (consequently entropies) of ionizations have also been determined calorimetrically at 298°K. The inadequacies of electrostatic theories in explaining the thermodynamic parameters have been stressed. The importance of ionic solvation and structural contributions, though not well-understood, have been discussed.

THE analytical applications of 1,10-phenanthroline (Ph) and its iron-complexes, ferroin and ferrin are well-known. The dissociation constants of 1,10-phenanthroline ion, ferroin and ferrin in aqueous solution have been determined by a large number of workers using different techniques¹.

The thermodynamic parameters of 1,10-phenanthroline were determined by Nasanen and Uusitalo² from temperature coefficient measurements of a cell without liquid-junction potential containing glass and Ag-AgCl electrodes. Lahiri and Aditya³ determined the thermodynamic properties of 1,10-phenanthroline ion and ferroin spectrophotometrically and that of ferrin using the data of George, Hanania and Irvine⁴. These values are in good agreement with the calorimetric values reported by Anderegg⁵. However, no systematic investigations have been made regarding the thermodynamic properties of the ligand and their complexes in solvents other than water. Such studies would be helpful in explaining the role of the solvents on the dissociation constants and other thermodynamic parameters and in gaining insight regarding the solute-solvent interactions.

Recently Lahiri, Biswas and Aditya⁶ reported the thermodynamics of 1,10-phenanthroline ion in ethanol-water solvents.

In order to elucidate the role of the solvents on the dissociation constants and the thermodynamic properties

of the isoelectric reactions of the type,

We studied the dissociation constants as well as enthalpies of the reactions (1), (2) and (3) in methanol-water mixtures *pH*-metrically, spectrophotometrically and calorimetrically. The results are reported in the present communication.

Experimental

The stock solution of the ligand was prepared by dissolving the weighed amount of 1,10-phenanthroline hydrate (E. Merck) in the desired solvents. Perchloric acid, caustic soda and acetic acid used were of analar grade. The solutions were prepared using double-distilled water from an all-glass apparatus. The preparation of ferrous-ammonium sulphate solution and purification of methanol have been described earlier⁷.

The weight percentage of organic solvents in mixtures were determined in the same way as described before⁸. The dielectric constants of the solvent mixtures were calculated from the data by Bates and Robinson⁹.

For the dissociation constants of the ligands in different percentages of mixed solvents, sodium acetate and acetic acid buffers as well as perchloric acid solutions were used.

The measurements were taken in solutions of very low ionic strengths (10^{-3} – $10^{-4}M$) so that the dissociation constant values may be taken as the thermodynamic values.

The pK 's of 1,10-phenanthroline ion in methanol-water mixtures were determined spectrophotometrically in the manner described earlier.

The accuracy of the pK -values determined spectrophotometrically was further tested from pH -titration described earlier⁶. The average pK -values are given in table I.

The concentrations of the complex were determined from O.D. readings and extinction coefficient values at these wavelengths. The average value of concentration of the complex was obtained from these measurements.

For the measurement of enthalpy of formation of 1,10-phenanthroline ion in mixed solvents, excess of $HClO_4$ acid (concentration 0.2 N) was taken in the reaction Dewar. Spectrophotometric readings were taken with a Beckman D.U. spectrophotometer. The pH -readings were taken with Cambridge Bench type battery-operated pH -meter. The calorimeter used and the details of the enthalpy measurements have been described earlier^{11,12}.

TABLE I—MEAN pK VALUES FOR 1,10-PHENANTHROLINE ION AND FERROIN IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 298°K

Wt. % of Methanol	pK_T for $PhH^+ \rightleftharpoons Ph + H^+$		Extinction coefficient values at		pK_a for reaction $FePh_3^{2+} + 3H^+ \rightleftharpoons Fe^{2+} + 3PhH^+$ using calculated H^+ ion concentration	pK for $FePh_3^{2+} \rightleftharpoons Fe^{2+} + 3Ph$ using calculated H^+ ion concentration
	pH -meter	Spectrophotometer	500 nm.	510 nm.		
8	4.88	4.90	10745	11107	5.44	20.08
16.4	4.75	4.80	10907	11158	5.56	19.81
25.2	4.63	4.63	11152	11358	5.66	19.55
34.4	4.56	4.57	10914	11440	5.37	19.05
44.1	4.31	4.35	11026	11553	5.57	18.50
54.2	4.17	4.19	11356	11645	5.12	17.63
64.7	4.00	3.97	10577	10999	4.32	16.32
75.9	3.80	3.76	10611	10852	4.18	15.58
87.7	3.86	3.87	10708	11063	3.6	15.27

Ferrous-1,10-phenanthroline complex has an absorption maximum at 510 nm. The addition of methanol in the medium has no effect on the absorption band.

Under our experimental conditions, $FePh_3^{2+}$ was assumed to be the sole species¹⁰ formed without any $FePh^{2+}$ and $FePh_2^+$. The extinction coefficients of ferroin at 500 and 510 nm were determined from O. D. readings of solutions containing 10 to 20 fold excess of ligand to different amounts of ferrous ion where complete conversion of Fe^{2+} to $FePh_3^{2+}$ took place. The extinction coefficients of ferroin in different mixed solvents are given in columns 4 and 5 of table 1.

For the determination of stability constants of ferroin in mixed solvents, O. D.'s of solutions containing different amounts of Fe^{2+} ion (concn. range $5-25 \times 10^{-5} M$) and phenanthroline (concn. range $5-25 \times 10^{-5} M$) were measured at 500 and 510 nm. The pH 's ranged from 2.80 to 3.80.

Results

The thermodynamic dissociation constant K_T^+ for the equilibrium $PhH^+ \rightleftharpoons Ph + H^+$ is given by

$$K_T = \frac{a_{Ph} \times a_{H^+}}{a_{PhH^+}} = \frac{C_{Ph} \times C_{H^+}}{C_{PhH^+}} \cdot \frac{f_{Ph} \times f_{H^+}}{f_{PhH^+}} \quad \dots (4)$$

In our measurements, the hydrogen ion concentrations were of the order of 10^{-3} – $10^{-4}M$ and the ionic strengths of the solutions were of the order of $10^{-2}M$ (even if acetate buffers were used), therefore, $\frac{f_{Ph} \times f_{H^+}}{f_{PhH^+}}$ can be approximated to unity.

$$\text{Thus, } pK_T = pH + \log[C_{PhH^+}/C_{Ph}] = [B] + \log U_H^+ + \log[C_{PhH^+}/C_{Ph}]$$

$$= [B] + \log U_H^+ + \log[(d_M - d)/(d - d_1)] \quad \dots (5)$$

where [B] = meter reading in mixed solvents,

$\log U_H$ = correction factor in mixed solvent, and

d_M, d_1 and d' are optical densities of the ligand in the molecular form, ionic form and at intermediate pH 's. Knowing [B], $\log U_H, d_M, d_1$ and d' values at different percentages of the mixed solvents, pK_T values are determined.

For determination of pK by pH -metry, $\log [C_{PhH^+}/C_{Ph}]$ was determined from the fraction of neutralisation. Though the correction factors were known¹², yet we considered it desirable to calibrate the glass electrode before each of the measurement in the way described before¹³⁻¹⁵ to avoid any error creeping in the measurements due to changed asymmetry potential and sensitivity of the glass electrode.

Dissociation constants of ferriin complex

The equilibrium between ferriin and a strong acid may be represented as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thus, } K_a &= \frac{C_{Fe^{2+}} \times C_{PhH^+} \times f_{Fe^{2+}} \times f_{PhH^+}^3}{C_{FePh_3^{2+}} \times C_{H^+}^3 \times f_{FePh_3^{2+}} \times f_{H^+}^3} \\ &= K \times f_{Fe^{2+}} \times f_{H^+}^3 / f_{FePh_3^{2+}} \times f_{H^+}^3 \quad \dots (6) \end{aligned}$$

Since, the measurements were made at very low ionic strengths, it is reasonable to assume $f_{Fe^{2+}} = f_{FePh_3^{2+}}$ and $f_{PhH^+} = f_{H^+}$, thus K_a becomes equal to K_c . The equilibrium constant values were evaluated using calculated values of H^+ ion concentrations.

The equilibrium constants K for the reaction, $FePh_3^{2+} \rightleftharpoons Fe^{2+} + 3Ph$,

$$\text{given by } K = \frac{[Fe^{2+}][Ph]^3}{[FePh_3^{2+}]} \quad \dots (7)$$

is related to the equilibrium constants of reactions (1) and (2) in different solvents by the equation,

$$K = K_a \times K_T^3. \quad \dots (8)$$

The values of the equilibrium constants are given in columns, 2,3, 6 and 7 of table 1.

The enthalpy values from the relation

$$\Delta H = -\frac{Q}{C} \quad \dots (9)$$

where Q is the amount of heat evolved for the conversion of C grammoles of the Ph or Fe^{2+} into PhH^+ or $FePh_3^{2+}$ as under our experimental conditions all the ligands Λ or Fe^{2+} will be converted into PhH^+ or $FePh_3^{2+}$.

The ΔH values for reactions (1) and (3) are given in table 2. The effect of ionic strengths on the isoelectric reactions (1) is small and so ΔH_1 can be taken as ΔH_1^0 .

The ΔH^0 values for reaction (2) can be calculated from ΔH^0 values for reactions (1) and (3). The thermodynamic properties $\Delta G^0, \Delta H^0$ and ΔS^0 for the reactions (1), (2) and (3) are given in table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMICS OF IONISATION OF PHENANTHROLIUM ION AND FERROIN IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 298°K

Reaction Wt. % of MeOH	PhH ⁺ ⇌ Ph + H ⁺			FePh ₃ ²⁺ + 3H ⁺ ⇌ Fe ²⁺ + 3PhH ⁺				FePh ₃ ²⁺ ⇌ Fe ²⁺ + 3Ph	
	ΔG°/kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH°/kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS°/ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG°/ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH°/ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS°/ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG°/ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH°/ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS°/ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
0	28.83 ^(a)	17.03 (±0.20)	-39.8	30.46	80.63	168.2	116.90	131.04	47.3 ^(a)
8.0	27.82 (±0.10)	18.37 (±0.20)	-31.8	31.05	87.77	190.3	114.56	142.88 (±1.0)	95.0
16.4	27.11	26.23	-2.9	31.71	83.51	173.9	113.01	162.21	165.1
25.2	26.40	21.67	-15.9	32.30	105.60	246.0	111.55	170.62	198.3
34.4	26.02	19.04	-23.5	30.63	103.72	251.0	108.62	160.79	175.1
44.41	24.60	17.95	-22.2	31.76	99.29	226.5	105.56	153.18	159.8
54.2	23.76	18.37	-18.2	29.20	89.79	202.6	160.58	144.68	148.0]
64.7	22.80	17.20 (±0.20)	-18.9	24.64	106.11	273.4	93.14	157.65 (±2.0)	216.5
75.9	21.67	—	—	23.85	—	—	88.87	—	—
87.6	22.01 (±0.40)	—	—	21.05	—	—	87.11]	—	—

Discussions

The pK values of 1,10 phenanthrolium ion and ferroin in methanol-water mixtures are given in table 1. The pK-values of 1,10 phenanthrolium ion are found to be a linear function of (a) weight percent of methanol, (b) mole-fraction¹⁶ of methanol and (c) $1/\epsilon^{17}$ where ϵ is the relative permittivity¹⁷, upto 65% (wt) of methanol beyond which there are deviations. Only marginal improvement occurs if the activity of water is taken into consideration¹⁸. The pK-values in water may be had from the present measurement by extrapolation of any of these linear plots and these come out to be (a) 5.01, (b) 5.05 and (c) 5.03 in close agreement with our earlier value of 5.05 in water determined spectrophotometrically⁹. The results in columns 2 and 3 of table 1 show that the pK-values of 1,10 phenanthrolium ion passes through a minimum around 70 wt% of methanol similar to the observations by Paabo *et al*¹⁹, and Ohtaki²⁰. For the reaction (3), a similar variation in pK values as in the reaction (1) is noted except for the minimum around 70 wt% of alcohol. For the reaction(2), the pK values increase first and then decrease.

The increasingly negative values of ΔG° for reactions (1) and (3) with increasing concentration of methanol indicate that the reactions are favoured in mixed solvents. For the reaction (2), the initial addition of alcohol up to 44 wt%, the reaction is not favourable, further increase in alcohol concentration favours the process. This is not unexpected since

$$\Delta G^\circ_{(2)} = \Delta G^\circ_{(3)} - 3\Delta G^\circ_{(1)}$$

The analysis of the results in light of Born²¹ equation, despite its limitations, shows that the dielectric constant is not the major factor affecting ionization, the main factor being solute-solvent interactions. The increase in the solubility of 1,10 phenanthroline in methanol-water mixtures and the difference in the solvational properties of PhH^+ , H^+ , Fe^{3+} and FePh_3^{3+} are responsible for the variation in ΔG° values.

It has been said earlier that the structural modifications and ionic solvation have marked contribution to ΔH and ΔS but not on ΔG because of compensating

Fig. 1.

effects of ΔH and $T\Delta S$. Therefore the evaluation and interpretation of these parameters (ΔH and ΔS), though intriguing, seem worthwhile. The variations of ΔG° , ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ against mole fraction of methanol for the reactions (1), (2) and (3) are shown in the figure.

The values of ΔH for the reactions (1), (2) and (3) show appreciable variation with changes in solvent composition which is difficult to explain. Although there is lack of data in mixed solvents, wide variations of ΔH values have been reported for the ionization of water in DMSO-water mixtures^{22,23} at 25° in methanol-water mixtures²⁴ and for the ionization of 4-substituted phenols in methanol-water mixtures²⁵. The ΔH values by Avedikian²⁶ show an increase up to a mole fraction of 0.2 in alcohol in the case of ionization of acetic acid, but for benzoic acid ΔH shows a maximum around $x_2=0.3-0.4$, in methanol-water mixtures. These variations in ΔH with composition of solvent have been interpreted on the basis of variations in the structural properties of the solvent systems and ion-solvent interactions. Methanol-water system, it may be noted, shows a maximum in exothermic excess enthalpy of mixing at about $x_2 \approx 0.2$ (x_2 =mole fraction of methanol), a minimum in $T\Delta S$ at $x_2 \approx 0.3$ and a maximum in the positive free energy change of mixing around $x_2 \approx 0.5$ ²⁷.

Another process that needs mention is the preferential solvation of H^+ and Fe^{2+} compared to $FePh_3^{2+}$ and PhH^+ ions by water on the basis of electrostatic considerations, although the preferential solvation by the other solvent cannot be ruled out. Grunwald^{28,29} and coworkers showed that certain cations like Na^+ , K^+ , H_3O^+ may be solvated by dioxane rather than hydrated in 50% dioxane-water mixtures. Nothing can however, be spelt out specifically about the solvation of ions in alcohol-water mixtures. The free-energy of transfer $\Delta G_f^\circ(H^+)$ of solvated proton from water to methanol-water mixtures up to 50% w/w of methanol, according to Wells³⁰ is equivalent to the transfer of a tetrahedral aquo-proton from water into the mixture and subsequent replacement of an H_2O molecule in the tetrahedron by a methanol molecule,

Such processes have profound effect on the enthalpy, and entropy changes of the reactions.

The breaking of $>N \rightarrow H^+$ and $>N \rightarrow Fe$ bonds results in the increase of ΔH° and ΔS° values. The structure-breaking process is endothermic accompanied with an increase in entropy while the structure forming process is exothermic associated with entropy-decrease³¹⁻³³. Thus a number of interactions result in the variation of ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ of any reaction with composition of the solvent. ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ for the reaction (1) increase as the organic component increases and pass through maxima around $x_2 \approx 0.1$. The values of ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ for both reactions (2) and (3)

show similar maxima around $x_2 \approx 0.15$. The ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ curves for reactions (1), (2) and (3), in general, show similar features. From the results one could infer that an overall increase in the structure of the solvent occurs which passes through a maximum around $x_2 \approx 0.15$. Similar observations have been made by Stern and Hansen³⁴ and Arnett³⁷ et al. This is also in agreement with the maxima reported for heats of solution of electrolytes in methanol-water around 20 mole per cent of methanol^{38,39} and also with our earlier reports on 2,2' dipyridyl and its iron(II) complexes⁴⁰ in ethanol.

Although the general nature of the ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ curves is the same, a comparison of the values of ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ for 2,2' dipyridyl and its ferrous complexes with those of 1,10 phenanthroline and its complexes in methanol-water mixtures show considerable differences in the magnitude of the thermodynamic parameters. In case of dipyridinium and phenanthrolium and their tris complexes with iron(II) in water, the difference in ΔH was accounted for by Lahiri and Aditya³ in terms of the difference in the resonance stabilisation energy of 1,10 phenanthroline and 2,2'-dipyridyl. In mixed solvents the difference is found to be changing with solvent composition. In addition to the difference in resonance stabilisation energy, the other factors that possibly come into play are (a) the hydrogen bonding capability of 1,10 phenanthroline and 2,2' dipyridyl, (b) the fixed coplanarity of heterocyclic rings of phenanthroline compared to 2,2' dipyridyl⁴¹ and (c) the presence of dipyridyl predominantly as 'trans' form in water or in mixed solvents. The change in the enthalpy of protonation may be regarded as involving two equilibria, viz.,

The first step is endothermic and the second an exothermic process⁴². For both the processes ΔH may be dependent on the composition of the medium.

With our present state of knowledge in the field, it is not possible to explain quantitatively the difference in the values of ΔH and $T\Delta S$ for 1,10 phenanthroline and 2,2' dipyridyl and their iron(II) complexes methanol mixtures.

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